

ACTUAL SPEECH DIVISION IN LINGUISTICS

Akhatova Kumushkhon Qurbonali qizi

Master of FSU

Yusupova Sabohat A'zamjonovna

Senior teacher of FSU

Abstract First of all, we need to know that actualization means actuality and importance. The order of the sentence plays an important role in the actualization of a certain part of the sentence. Nowadays, the issue of actual division of the sentence and word order is of great importance. is taken and the actual division of the sentence is studied as an important communicative-syntactic phenomenon in relation to the order of words. In this article, actualizing tools are studied. Important actualizers include: prosodic actualizer, emphatic-emotional accent (emotion is strong in emphatic accent, vowel or consonant is lengthened), lexical and grammatical actualizer (only, alone, even, itself words and suffixes like -gina, -aq, -yak) were given.

Key words: sentence division, inversion, normal order, changed order, theme, rheme.

Introduction: Since the speech has an individual nature, the composition of the word forms participating in the sentence is also free. However, this "freedom" will never be outside the framework of general linguistic laws. Based on the speaker's purpose and stylistic requirements, the word forms have a general order.

Any speech, in addition to expressing a certain reality, also shows the informational goal of the speaker. For example, in the sentence Jasur went home, along with the fact that Jasur went home, the intention of the speaker to convey information about where Jasur went to the listener is also reflected. So where did Jasur go? there will be an answer to the question. So, the reality in this sentence is not where Jasur went,

but who went where, and the speaker's information goal is to convey information about where Jasur went to the listener.

If we change the sentence in the form of "The brave man went home", the reality is the same as in the previous sentence, but the speaker's information goal is "Who went home?" It is determined through the question. In the first sentence, the direction of the action, in the second sentence, the executor of the action is the information target. The structure of the sentence from the point of view of the information function is called actual structure. The components of the actual structure are called actual fragments.

From the point of view of the actual task, the elements that make up the sentence are divided into theme (known) and rheme (new) parts. The rhema part of the sentence is important from a communicative (informational) point of view. The question is asked to determine this rheme. If the subject part of the sentence is known, it is repeated exactly in the interrogative sentence.

Literature analysis and methodology

The more words in a sentence, the more words are stressed. However, no matter how broad or narrow the sentence is, it has the same logical emphasis. Which part of the sentence has a logical emphasis is the rheme, and the rest of the sentence is the theme. In sentences consisting of possessor and participle only, whichever part gets logical stress, it gets the status of rheme. 1. Karim has arrived. Karim - theme, came - rheme. 2. Karim came. Karim - rema, came -tema.

Emphatic emotional emphasis. Emphatic stress also distinguishes a certain word form in a sentence. This makes it look like a logical accent. However, in contrast to logical emphasis, emphatic emphasis is strongly emotional. In Uzbek, a vowel or consonant in a word under emphatic stress is lengthened. For example: The weather is t-o-za. Ch-i-roy girl came. Emphasis is also expressed as a result of repeating words: If I go, I.

In words under logical and emphatic emphasis, a pause also participates as an auxiliary tool. In most cases, there is a pause before the words that receive this accent.

Discussion and results

Various lexical and grammatical forms in the Uzbek language also participate in the actualization of a certain word form. These tools come with a logical accented word form and are a logical auxiliary actualizing tool. These include the words only, alone, even, himself and the suffixes -gina, -oq,-yoq

Even Javohir did the job.

Anora also studied.

Asliddin ran and jumped.

You say it yourself.

Only Salima understands.

The fragment that comes with this lexical-grammatical tool is actualized with a logical emphasis - it becomes a rheme.

Communicative indivisible sentences. Not every sentence has a theme-rhematic division. There are sentences of such a form that they can be called communicative indivisible sentences. There is no theme (known information) in such sentences. The whole thing will consist of only rheme. The informative function of such sentences is to express the existence or occurrence of an event. 1. Climbing the mountain today. 2. Spring. 3. The cold has begun. 4. He came in late. 5. Thank you. Communicative integrity is related to more consistent content of sentences. In participle sentences with two components, this sentence is connected with the semantics of the sentence. 1. It's morning. 2. Dusk fell. The semantic structure of such sentences is almost similar to monosyllabic sentences.

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